

Urine Bilirubin Related With the Milk Likeliness

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ABSTRACT

The aim of present study was to relate the urine bilirubin with milk likeliness. Bilirubin is a substance of yellow color produced during normal process of body when red blood cells are broken down. It is fluid present in the liver. It helps in the digestion process of body. If bilirubin is present in the urine it may be sign of liver disordered. A urine test was performed by using urine strips for this purpose. The students which show positive sign for urine bilirubin had more attention towards milk drinking as compare to the students with negative sign.

Keywords: Urine bilirubin, Milk likeliness.

1. INTRODUCTION

Bilirubin is a substance of yellow color produced during normal process of body when red blood cells are broken down. It is fluid present in the liver. It helps in the digestion process of body. If bilirubin is present in the urine it may be sign of liver disordered.

Chemical change is occurring in bilirubin by the liver when it excreted in the urine. If the rate of breaking of red blood cells is higher than concentration of bilirubin is also higher. It is waste product that is produced by the destruction of old red blood cells.

Bilirubin is similar to the phycobilin. Z-Z-isomer is natural isomer of the bilirubin. It has an open chain structure. The higher concentration of bilirubin in urine has harmful effects on human health. Milk is a useful product for many purposes it is used in most of the food products such as yogurt, cheese, and ice creams. Yogurt is a pro-biotic which contain beneficial effects on human health.

It has various types of microbes which protect our digestive system. It reduces the risks of many diseases. It is obtained by many animals such as cows, buffaloes and goats.

The aim of present study was to relate the urine bilirubin with milk likeliness.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

The students which show positive sign for urine bilirubin had A urine test was performed by using urine strips for this purpose. It was worn to verify the attendance of bilirubin in urine. First of all took urine samples and dip in the urine strip. Consequences were raised. In this way a mixture of changes in urine or presence of blood can be tartan.

3. OBJECTIVE OF THE STUDY

A simple study is deliberated to show a bond between milk likeliness and blood in urine.

4. STATISTICAL ANALYSIS

M state was used for this intention.

5. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Urine test was performed to check the various changes in urine analysis and presence of bilirubin in urine. Hundreds students were drawn in in this work. Some people had encouraging results and some people had harmful results. They had diverse tastes for milk likeliness according to their urine intelligence. Males and females also had different choices.

Gender	Milk likeliness	Milk dis-likeliness
Male	72.72%	27.27%
Female	70%	30%

Males had more attraction towards milk than females.

6. CONCLUSION

The students with positive signs more attention towards milk drinking as compare to the students with negative signs.

Declarations

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Competing Interests Statement

The authors declare no competing financial, professional, or personal interests.

Consent for publication

The authors declare that they consented to the publication of this research work.

Authors' Contributions

All authors equally contributed to research and paper drafting.

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